

THE NECESSITY OF TEACHING VOCABULARY.

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Introduction: In recent years, Uzbekistan is going to make rapid strides in all spheres. Changes are quick and inevitable. Integration of our state into the international community, development of science and technology requires that the younger generation for competitive functioning in the multicultural world well knew several foreign languages. Knowledge of a foreign language - one of components of professional competence of specialists of any profile.

Today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan great attention is given to the radical reorganization of the educational system that will give an opportunity to raise it to the level of modern standards.

New approaches in the system of education also influenced on the learning and teaching of foreign languages, as language is the major factor of person's development.

Topic analysis: Vocabulary of a language is just like bricks for constructing a building. Like bricks, they are vital for the building of a language. Language is made up of words. If we want to use language effectively, we must have good stock of vocabulary. We cannot use the language, if we don't know the words of that language. English language has vast vocabulary. It is the richest language of the world. One cannot learn a language without learning vocabulary. Therefore, the study of vocabulary has occupied the central place in teaching learning activities.

Thornbury opines (2002) “If you spend most of your time studying grammar, your English will not improve very much. You will see most improvement, if you learn more words and expressions. You can say very little with grammar, but you can say almost anything with words.” This speaks volumes about the significance of vocabulary in learning, developing and enriching English. Even, Wilkins rightly says, “Without grammar very little can be conveyed....but without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed” (p.111, quotes in Lewis, 2000). Vocabulary is a very important means to express our thoughts and feeling, either in spoken or written form. Indeed, neither literature nor language exists without vocabulary. John Drink Water rightly says that words are the bricks the bricks with which the poetry and the literature of the world have been built. It is mainly through using words that we compose and express our thoughts to others. We can tackle our own task through words. It shows words are powerful tools. Famous imperialist poet, Rudyard Kipling says that words are the most powerful drug used by mankind. Those who are rich in vocabulary can speak and write English correctly. Therefore, the study of vocabulary is at the center while learning a new language. English being a second language or foreign language, one needs to learn vocabulary in the systematic way. In fact, without vocabulary communication in a second or foreign language is not possible in a meaningful way. McCarthy (1990) argues: 'No matter how well the student learns grammar, no matter how successfully the sounds of L2 are mastered, without words to express a wide range of meanings, communication in an L2 just cannot happen in any meaningful way'. Vocabulary is needed for expressing meaning and in using the receptive (listening and reading) and the productive (speaking and writing) skills. It should be considered as an internal part of learning a foreign language since it leads the way to communication. Nation and Waring (1997), aptly mentioned, “Such as writing and reading , vocabulary knowledge is one of the components of language skills”. Harmer clearly states, “ if language structures make up the skeleton of language, then it is vocabulary that provides the vital organs and the flesh”. If one wants to use language effectively, he/she must have good stock of vocabulary. Language is made up of words. According to Throat

et.al (2001), 'Words are the building block of language'. Nagy(2003) appropriately remarks, "Vocabulary knowledge is fundamental to reading comprehension; one cannot understand text without knowing what most of the words mean". Teaching vocabulary well is a key aspect of developing engaged and successful readers. "There is a great divide between what we know about vocabulary instruction and what we (often, still) do"(Greenwood, 2004, p. 28). Traditional vocabulary instruction for many teachers involves having students look words up in the dictionary, write definitions, and use words in sentences (Basurto, 2004). Word lists, teacher explanation, discussion, memorization, vocabulary books, and quizzes often are used in an effort to help students learn new words. But these methods ignore what research and theory tell us about word learning and sound vocabulary instruction. Vocabulary is a principle contributor to comprehension, fluency, and achievement. What need to be taught? Nowadays methodologists and linguists suggest that teachers can decide and select the words to be taught on the basis of how frequently they are used by speakers of the language. CarterMcCarthy(1991) rightly points out, "Knowing a word involves knowing its spoken and written context of use; its patterns with words of related meaning as well as with its collocation partners; its syntactic, pragmatic and discourse patterns;. It means knowing it actively and productively as well as receptively.": Richards (1976) list the different things teaching need to know about a word before we can say that they have taught it.

Effective Ways of Teaching Vocabulary.

Different types of instructional modes, approaches, vocabulary building activities and skills proved to be effective in developing children and college students' vocabulary in L2 environments. Teaching vocabulary in context, combining vocabulary with reading and writing activities, and providing the students with different lexical information about the words under study enhanced students' vocabulary. The prominent role of vocabulary knowledge in second or foreign language learning has been recently recognized by the theorist and

researcher in the field. Accordingly, numerous types of approaches, techniques, exercises and practice to teach vocabulary. Nation properly states that teaching vocabulary should not only consist of teaching specific words but also aims at equipping learners with strategies necessary to expand their vocabulary knowledge.

By showing actual objects and showing models.

It is a very useful technique to teach vocabulary to the beginners. The names of many things can be taught by showing actual objects. It gives real experience and sense to the learners. The words like pen, chalk, table, chair, football, flowers, tomato etc. can be taught in the classroom. Real objects or models of real objects are very effective and meaningful in showing meanings but in handling of real objects, a teacher must be practical and should not be superfluous. It is neither possible nor necessary to bring all the things in the classroom. Therefore, some words are to be taught by showing models. They are easily available in the market. They are inexpensive too. Hence, teacher should make frequent use of such models to teach vocabulary. For example, the words like tiger, brain, elephant, aeroplane etc. can be shown to the learner.

Using demonstrations and showing pictures.

Teacher can perform some words. It can be fun and frolic. It makes the class student-centered. Teacher can act and learners try to imitate it. For example, the words like jump, smile, cry, nap, sleep, and dance can be demonstrated. Miming works well with younger students. You can mime out emotions and everyday activities to teach new words. This method can be practiced at ease. It can win the favour of the students as learners like dramatizations and can easily learn through them. Many situations can be dramatized or demonstrated. This works well with young students or students studying a foreign language to help introduce them to new concepts. After explaining new vocabulary, you can then ask the students to perform the actions. Charts, pictures and maps can be used to develop students' understanding of a particular concept or word. There are some good picture

dictionaries available in the market. Teacher should make use of such dictionaries. For instance, using a picture of a 'fish', words related to the fish, such as gills, eyes, backbone, cold-blooded, water, big, small etc. can be taught. Zebrowska rightly says, 'Learners remember better the material that has been presented by means of visual aids'. Some words work well with pictures, particularly nouns. This can also be a good way to introduce blocks of related words, which is often utilized in foreign language classes, such as nouns and verbs related to the classroom or the house. Pictures can also be used in printable worksheets and flashcards, where pictures are matched to the word they represent.

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